

CaSnO₃: Yb³⁺, Er³⁺, Ho³⁺ system synthesis and study of its luminescence under IR excitation

Ul'ana A. Mar'ina¹, Viktor A. Vorob'ev¹, Alexandr P. Mar'in¹

1 North-Caucasus Federal University, 1 Pushkina Str., Stavropol 355009, Russia

Corresponding author: Ul'ana A. Mar'ina (ulyana-ne@mail.ru)

Received 13 July 2017 ♦ Accepted 10 May 2018 ♦ Published 1 June 2018

Citation: Mar'ina UA, Vorob'ev VA, Mar'in AP (2018) CaSnO₃: Yb³⁺, Er³⁺, Ho³⁺ system synthesis and study of its luminescence under IR excitation. *Modern Electronic Materials* 4(2): 71–75. <https://doi.org/10.3897/j.moem.4.2.38545>

Abstract

Solid state synthesis of Perovskite-like calcium stannate structure activated with three rare-Earth metal ions Yb³⁺, Er³⁺, Ho³⁺ has been studied. The formation of the CaSnO₃: Yb³⁺, Er³⁺, Ho³⁺ luminescent structure requires the following synthesis conditions: anneal temperature 1250 °C and duration at least 18 h. The luminescent properties of the specimens have been studied under 960 nm semiconductor diode laser excitation. The luminescence spectra contain bands in the visible and IR spectral regions. Yb³⁺ ions have been shown to act predominantly as sensitizers capable of transferring part of absorbed energy to Er³⁺ and Ho³⁺ ions thus intensifying their respective luminescence peaks. Er³⁺ ions also transfer part of absorbed energy to Ho³⁺ ions leading to an increase in the intensity of the 1194 and 1950 nm IR luminescence bands. A schematic of possible energy transitions in the CaSnO₃: Yb³⁺, Er³⁺, Ho³⁺ system under 960 nm laser excitation has been suggested. The energy transfer mechanism between Yb³⁺, Er³⁺ and Ho³⁺ ions has been described in detail. The luminescence intensity of the luminophore has been studied at 994, 1194, 1550 and 1950 nm as a function of Ho³⁺ ion concentration. The peak intensity of the 1194 and 1950 nm bands is the highest at a Ho³⁺ ion concentration of 0.007 at.fr. It has been suggested to use the CaSnO₃: Yb³⁺, Er³⁺, Ho³⁺ luminescent structure for radiation sources capable of converting 960 nm IR radiation to ~2000 nm IR radiation.

Keywords

luminescence, infrared luminophores, solid state synthesis, rare-Earth elements

1. Introduction

CaSnO₃ base compounds pertaining to MSnO₃ type Perovskite-like stannates find increasing application due to their universal electromagnetic properties. Currently they are of interest for multiple fields of electronics engineering as materials of cathodes, thermally stable capacitors, photocatalysts, gas or humidity sensors etc. [1, 2]. The luminescent properties of rare-Earth metal stannates have been studied insufficiently yet, most works dealing with

calcium stannate compounds emitting visible radiation [3–6]. There are only a few works on IR luminescence of calcium stannate compounds in the 900–1600 nm region [7, 8]. No information on the luminescent properties of Perovskite-like stannates in the 1700–2000 nm region was available to us at the time we made this work. Therefore study of the luminescent properties of CaSnO₃ base compounds in this spectral region is an important research task.

Earlier experimental data for $\text{CaSnO}_3 : \text{Yb}^{3+}$, $\text{CaSnO}_3 : \text{Er}^{3+}$ and $\text{CaSnO}_3 : \text{Ho}^{3+}$ single-activator luminescent structures and double-activator $\text{CaSnO}_3 : \text{Yb}^{3+}, \text{Er}^{3+}$ and $\text{CaSnO}_3 : \text{Yb}^{3+}, \text{Ho}^{3+}$ luminescent structures indicated energy transfer from Yb^{3+} ions to Er^{3+} и Ho^{3+} ones. This transfer increases the 1550 and 1950 nm luminescence band intensities, respectively. Below we consider the mechanism of energy transformation in the $\text{Yb}^{3+}-\text{Er}^{3+}-\text{Ho}^{3+}$ combination and the possibility of increasing IR luminescence intensity near 1950 nm by energy transfer to Ho^{3+} ions from Yb^{3+} and Er^{3+} ones. To solve this task we synthesized series of specimens with the general formula $(\text{Ca}_{1-x-y-z}\text{Yb}_x\text{Er}_y\text{Ho}_z)\text{SnO}_3$ and studied their luminescent properties.

2. Experimental

At the first stage we tested different solid state synthesis modes and selected optimum anneal temperature and time for pure CaSnO_3 . The source components were calcium carbonate CaCO_3 and tin hydroxide $\text{Sn}(\text{OH})_2$ which were dry mixed in the 1 : 1 stoichiometric ratio. After thorough grinding the charge was sieved (# 100 mesh), loaded into alundum crucibles and placed in a high-temperature furnace for heat treatment. The experiments showed that the formation of the pure CaSnO_3 phase requires specimen annealing in an oxidizing atmosphere at 1250 °C for 18 h [9].

At the second stage we obtained calcium stannate specimens activated with rare-Earth metal ions. The charge composition was calculated based on the formula $(\text{Ca}_{1-x-y-z}\text{Yb}_x\text{Er}_y\text{Ho}_z)\text{SnO}_3$. The x , y and z indices in the formula correspond to the content of each element in the luminophore in atomic fractions. Since the luminescent properties of the test structures are sensitive to impurities the $\text{CaSnO}_3 : \text{Yb}^{3+}, \text{Er}^{3+}, \text{Ho}^{3+}$ system was synthesized from special purity Yb_2O_3 , Er_2O_3 and Ho_2O_3 rare-Earth element oxides that were added to the charge in the form of nitrate solutions. The Yb^{3+} ion concentration in the specimens was constant, 0.05 at.fr.. According to earlier data [10] this concentration provides for the highest 996 nm luminescence band intensity for the $(\text{Ca}_{0.95}\text{Yb}_{0.05})\text{SnO}_3$ system under 960 nm excitation. The Er^{3+} ion concentration was 0.02 at.fr. and also constant. This concentration provides for the highest 1550 nm luminescence band intensity for the $(\text{Ca}_{0.93}\text{Yb}_{0.05}\text{Er}_{0.02})\text{SnO}_3$ system under 960 nm optical laser excitation [11]. The Ho^{3+} ion concentration varied from 0.00005 to 0.1 at.fr.. Calcium carbonate and rare-Earth element nitrate solutions were mixed in liquid state and then the specimens were placed into a drying chamber for 2 h. Then a tin hydroxide and flux mixture was added to the charge, and the mixture was thoroughly grinded and sieved. Then the charge was loaded into alundum crucibles and annealed at 1250 °C for 18 h. The SnCl_2 (3 wt.%), Li_2CO_3 (1 wt.%) and Na_2CO_3 (1 wt.%) fluxes were added to the luminophore charge for reducing the melting point and increasing the solution component diffusion rate. Furthermore Li^+ and Na^+ alkaline metal ions act as compensating impurities. They partially compensate

the charge mismatch produced by Ca^{2+} ion substitution for Yb^{3+} , Er^{3+} and Ho^{3+} ions in CaSnO_3 lattice sites [5, 12, 13].

The phase composition of the as-synthesized specimens was studied on a DIFRAY-401 X-ray diffractometer (CuK_α radiation, Ni filter). The unit cell parameters were calculated using the Diffract software. The grain size distribution of the powders was studied using a Microsizer-201A laser particle size analyzer. The luminescence and excitation spectra were taken in the 400–2100 nm range using an MDR-41 monochromator, FEU-62 and FEU-100 photoelectron amplifiers and a 960 nm pulse semiconductor diode laser.

3. Results and discussion

Calcium stannate CaSnO_3 has a perovskite-like orthorhombic crystalline structure with the $Pbnm$ space symmetry group. Calcium stannate doping with rare-Earth element ions when Yb^{3+} , Er^{3+} and Ho^{3+} ions substitute Ca^{2+} rare-Earth metal ions does not change the crystal lattice symmetry [14–16]. Figure 1 shows X-ray phase analysis data for the pure calcium stannate specimens synthesized at a constant temperature and different anneal times and for rare-Earth ion activated calcium stannate.

The position and intensity of the diffraction peaks correspond to the CaSnO_3 phase. The sharp diffraction peaks indicate the high crystallinity of the specimens. Grain size distribution analysis shows the average particle size of the $(\text{Ca}_{0.93-x}\text{Yb}_{0.05}\text{Er}_{0.02}\text{Ho}_{0.007})\text{SnO}_3$ structure to be 30.5 μm .

$(\text{Ca}_{0.93-x}\text{Yb}_{0.05}\text{Er}_{0.02}\text{Ho}_z)\text{SnO}_3$ structure excitation with 960 nm visible laser radiation produces anti-Stokes luminescence in the 540–560 nm and 640–690 nm bands (Fig. 2).

The 540–560 nm band does not show any clear holmium ion concentration dependence of luminescence intensity since this spectrum region is a superposition of luminescence peaks for multiple activators. The 545 nm peak for a 0.007 at.fr. Ho^{3+} ion concentration is produced

Figure 1. Diffraction patterns of CaSnO_3 specimens synthesized with (1) 1, (2) 10 and (3) 18 h anneal time and (4) $\text{CaSnO}_3 : \text{Yb}^{3+}, \text{Er}^{3+}, \text{Ho}^{3+}$ specimen synthesized for 18 h. The synthesis temperature was 1250 °C for all specimens.

Figure 2. Visible luminescence spectra of $(Ca_{0.93-x}Yb_{0.05}Er_{0.02}Ho_z)SnO_3$ specimens ($z = 0.00005; 0.0005; 0.007$) for 960 nm laser excitation: $z = (1) 0.00005$ at.fr.; (2) 0.0005 at.fr.; (3) 0.007 at.fr.

by the $^5F_4 \rightarrow ^5I_8$ transition in holmium ions. The two other peaks in this band for 0.0005 and 0.00005 at.fr. holmium ion concentrations are at 545 and 550 nm and produced by the $^5F_4 \rightarrow ^5I_8$ transition in holmium ions and the $^4S_{3/2} \rightarrow ^4I_{15/2}$ transition in erbium ions, respectively. The luminescence intensity in the 640–690 nm band decreases with increasing Ho^{3+} ion concentration in the luminophore. The luminescent peaks in this region are produced by the $^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4I_{15/2}$ transition in Er^{3+} ions. Similar anti-Stokes luminescence was observed in the visible spectral region earlier [8, 13].

Weak luminescence was observed in the ~740–770 nm near IR region. This luminescence is produced by the $^5I_4 \rightarrow ^5I_8$ transition in Ho^{3+} ions (Fig. 3).

As the Ho^{3+} ion concentration increases to 0.00005 at.fr. the luminescence intensity in this band increases and then decreases due to the concentration quenching of luminescence.

960 nm excitation of the material also produces IR luminescence bands peaking at ~996, 1194, 1550 and 1950 nm (Fig. 4).

The radiation in these bands corresponds to the following transitions:

- 996 nm band: $^2F_{5/2} \rightarrow ^2F_{7/2}$ transition in Yb^{3+} ions;
- 1194 nm band: $^5I_6 \rightarrow ^5I_8$ transition in Ho^{3+} ions;
- 1550 nm band: $^4I_{13/2} \rightarrow ^4I_{15/2}$ transition in Er^{3+} ions;
- 1950 nm band: $^5I_7 \rightarrow ^5I_8$ transition in Ho^{3+} ions.

Figure 3 shows that an increase in the Ho^{3+} ion concentration in the luminophore matrix increases the luminescence intensity in the bands corresponding to Ho^{3+} ions. However the bands corresponding to Yb^{3+} and Er^{3+} ions exhibit the contrary behavior. Earlier we reported that 811–960 nm laser excitation of specimens having a $(Ca_{1-x}Ho_x)SnO_3$ structure produces no luminescence but generates luminescence in the (Yb^{3+}, Ho^{3+}) and (Er^{3+}, Ho^{3+}) bands for the $(Ca_{1-x-y}Yb_xHo_y)SnO_3$ and $(Ca_{1-x-y}Er_xHo_y)SnO_3$ systems, respectively [10, 11]. Based on these data we concluded that these double-activator systems are activated through Yb^{3+}/Er^{3+} ions acting as excitation centers. Part of energy is transferred from excited energy levels

Figure 3. 740–775 nm luminescence spectra of $(Ca_{0.93-x}Yb_{0.05}Er_{0.02}Ho_z)SnO_3$ specimens for 960 nm laser excitation: $z = (1) 0.00005$ at.fr.; (2) 0.0005 at.fr.; (3) 0.007 at.fr.

Figure 4. 1000–2150 nm luminescence spectra of $(Ca_{0.93-x}Yb_{0.05}Er_{0.02}Ho_z)SnO_3$ specimens for 960 nm laser excitation: $z = (1) 0.00005$ at.fr.; (2) 0.0005 at.fr.; (3) 0.007 at.fr.

of Yb^{3+}/Er^{3+} ions to Ho^{3+} ion levels followed by optical transitions in Ho^{3+} ions. The weak luminescence intensity of the $(Ca_{1-x-y}Er_xHo_y)SnO_3$ specimens compared with the $(Ca_{1-x-y}Yb_xHo_y)SnO_3$ ones indicates that Yb^{3+} ions are more efficient sensibilizers than Er^{3+} ones under IR excitation.

The luminescence peak intensity redistribution (Fig. 4) also indicates energy transfer from Yb^{3+} and Er^{3+} ions to Ho^{3+} ones in the $(Ca_{0.93-x}Yb_{0.05}Er_{0.02}Ho_z)SnO_3$ luminescent system. The energy transformation mechanism in the $(Ca_{1-x-y-z}Yb_xEr_yHo_z)SnO_3$ triple-activator system can be described as follows.

1. Luminescent system excitation with a 960 nm source supplies sufficient energy for the core level electrons in Yb^{3+} ($^2F_{7/2}$) and Er^{3+} ($^4I_{15/2}$) ions to transit to the $^2F_{5/2}$ and $^4I_{11/2}$ excited states, respectively.
2. The energy absorbed by Yb^{3+} ions is spent for phonon energy, the $^2F_{5/2} \rightarrow ^2F_{7/2}$ radiative transition, energy transfer from the $^2F_{5/2}$ excited state of Yb^{3+} ions to top energy levels of Ho^{3+} and Er^{3+} ions (cooperative sensibilization) and resonance interaction between Yb^{3+} ($^2F_{5/2}$), Ho^{3+} (5I_6) and Er^{3+} ($^4I_{11/2}$) ions.

- Yb³⁺–Ho³⁺ ion pairs exhibit the following energy transformation processes: electron transition from the ²F_{5/2} excited level of Yb³⁺ ions to the ³K₈, ⁵F₂, ⁵F₃, ⁵S₂ and ⁵F₄ excited levels of Ho³⁺ ions followed by anti-Stokes luminescence, and resonance energy transfer from the ²F_{5/2} excited level of Yb³⁺ ions to the ⁵I₆ excited level of Ho³⁺ ions followed by Stokes IR luminescence.
- Yb³⁺–Er³⁺ ion pairs exhibit the following energy transformation processes: electron transition from the ²F_{5/2} excited level of Yb³⁺ ions to the ⁴F_{7/2} excited level of Er³⁺ ions followed by anti-Stokes luminescence, and resonance energy transfer from the ²F_{5/2} excited level of Yb³⁺ ions to the ⁴I_{11/2} excited level of Er³⁺ ions followed by Stokes IR luminescence in the 1550 nm band.
- Er³⁺–Ho³⁺ ion pairs exhibit the following energy transformation processes: resonance energy transfer from the ⁴I_{11/2} excited level of Er³⁺ ions to the ⁵I₆ excited level of Ho³⁺ ions followed by Stokes IR luminescence.

The diagram of the abovementioned energy transitions in the visible and IR regions is presented in Fig. 5. The diagram was plotted using earlier data on the electron state energies of Yb³⁺, Er³⁺ and Ho³⁺ ions [8, 17].

To specify more exactly the luminescence intensity in the 994, 1194, 1550 and 1950 nm bands as a function of Ho³⁺ ion concentration we synthesized an additional series of specimens with $z = 0.001, 0.007, 0.01, 0.05$ and 0.1 at.fr. (Fig. 6).

The luminescence intensity in the bands corresponding to ytterbium (994 nm) and erbium (1550 nm) ions is the highest at low Ho³⁺ concentrations and decreases gradually with an increase in the holmium concentration. On the contrary, the luminescence intensity in the 1194 and 1950 nm bands corresponding to radiative transitions in

Figure 6. (Ca_{0.93-x}Yb_{0.05}Er_{0.02}Ho_z)SnO₃ luminescence intensity as a function of Ho³⁺ concentration for (1) 994, (2) 1194, (3) 1550 and (4) 1950 bands.

holmium ions increases and peaks at $z = 0.007$. Further increase in the holmium ion concentration in the lumino-phore matrix crystalline lattice intensifies concentration quenching of luminescence.

We used the best (Ca_{0.943}Yb_{0.05}Ho_{0.007})SnO₃ double-activator composition as a reference specimen for assessing the radiation efficiency of the (Ca_{0.93-x}Yb_{0.05}Er_{0.02}Ho_z)SnO₃ system in the ~2000 nm band when measuring the luminescence spectra for the specimens of this series. The study showed that the (Ca_{0.923}Yb_{0.05}Er_{0.02}Ho_{0.007})SnO₃ triple-activator composition has a higher luminescence intensity than the (Ca_{0.943}Yb_{0.05}Ho_{0.007})SnO₃ reference specimen at a 0.007 at.fr. Ho³⁺ ion concentration. If the (Ca_{0.943}Yb_{0.05}Ho_{0.007})SnO₃ reference specimen intensity in the 1950 nm band is taken as 100%, the (Ca_{0.923}Yb_{0.05}Er_{0.02}Ho_{0.007})SnO₃ triple-activator composition specimen intensity is 25% higher in this band. This accounts for the experimentally observed increase in the holmium ion luminescence intensity in the ~2000 nm band.

Figure 5. Schematic diagram of energy transfer mechanism between Yb³⁺, Er³⁺ and Ho³⁺ ions in the (Ca_{1-x-y-z}Yb_xEr_yHo_z)SnO₃ system.

4. Summary

The interaction mechanism between Yb^{3+} , Er^{3+} and Ho^{3+} ions in the calcium stannate crystal lattice was described. The possibility of increasing IR radiation luminescence intensity in the 1950 nm region by energy transfer from Yb^{3+} and Er^{3+} ions to Ho^{3+} ones was experimentally confirmed. The energy transfer mechanism and the radiative transition probability are largely controlled by the Ho^{3+} ion concentration in the luminescent composition. The

highest luminescence intensity in the 1950 nm band corresponds to a 0.007 at. fr. Ho^{3+} ion concentration. The capability of the $\text{CaSnO}_3 : \text{Yb}^{3+}, \text{Er}^{3+}, \text{Ho}^{3+}$ luminescent system of converting near IR region radiation (960 nm) to greater wavelength radiation (~2000 nm) can be used for the fabrication of photoconverters, protective marks and markers and IR sources. 1500+ nm sources are widely used for information transmission via fiber optics communication lines and find increasing application in ophthalmology, detection/ranging and materials processing due to the eye-safety of this spectral region.

References

- Gavrilova L. Ya. *Metody sinteza i issledovanie perspektivnykh materialov* [Methods of synthesis and research of perspective materials]. Ekaterinburg: Ural State University named after A. M. Gorky, 2008, 74 p. (In Russ.)
- Li H., Castelli I. E., Thygesen K. S., Jacobsen K. W. Strain sensitivity of band gaps of Sn-containing semiconductors. *Phys. Rev. B*. 2015; 91(4): 045204 (1–6). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.91.045204>
- Bingfu Lei, Bin Li, Haoran Zhanga Wenlian Li. Preparation and luminescence properties of $\text{CaSnO}_3 : \text{Sm}^{3+}$ phosphor emitting in the reddish orange region. *Optical Materials*. 2007; 29(11): 1491–1494. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optmat.2006.07.011>
- Zhengwei Liu, Yingliang Liu. Synthesis and luminescent properties of a new green afterglow phosphor $\text{CaSnO}_3 : \text{Tb}$. *Mater. Chem. Phys.* 2005; 93(1): 129–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2005.02.032>
- Zuoqiu Liang, Jinsu Zhang, Jiashi Sun, Xiangping Li, Lihong Cheng, Haiyang Zhong, Shaobo Fu, Yue Tian, Baojiu Chen. Enhancement of green long lasting phosphorescence in $\text{CaSnO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ by addition of alkali ions. *Physica B: Condensed Matter*. 2013; 412: 36–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physb.2012.12.013>
- Jinsu Zhang, Baojiu Chen, Zuoqiu Liang, Xiangping Li, Jiashi Sun, Lihong Cheng, Haiyang Zhong. Optical transition and thermal quenching mechanism in $\text{CaSnO}_3 : \text{Eu}^{3+}$ phosphors. *J. Alloys and Comp.* 2014; 612: 204–209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2014.05.188>
- Orsi Gordo V., Tuncer Arslanli Y., Canimoglu A., Ayvacikli M., Galviro Gobato Y., Henini M., Can N. Visible to infrared low temperature luminescence of Er^{3+} , Nd^{3+} and Sm^{3+} in CaSnO_3 phosphors. *Appl. Radiation and Isotopes*. 2015; 99: 69–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apradiso.2015.02.019>
- Pang X. L., Jia C. H., Li G. Q., Zhang W. F. Bright white upconversion luminescence from $\text{Er}^{3+}\text{-Tm}^{3+}\text{-Yb}^{3+}$ doped CaSnO_3 powders. *Optical Mat.* 2011; 34(1): 234–238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optmat.2011.08.019>
- Mar'ina U. A., Vorob'ev V. A. Features of synthesis the perovskitopodobnykh of structures like MSnO_3 ($M = \text{Ba}, \text{Sr}, \text{Ca}$) and research of their luminescent properties. *Vestnik SKFU*. 2016; (1): 7–13. (In Russ.)
- Mar'ina U. A., Vorob'ev V. A. The study of fluorescent properties of calcium stannate CaSnO_3 , activated with rare earth metals. *Vestnik SKFU*. 2016; (4): 36–41. (In Russ.)
- Mar'ina U. A., Mar'in A. P., Vorob'ev V. A. Synthesis and study of luminescent properties of system $\text{CaSnO}_3 : \text{Yb}^{3+}, \text{RE}^{3+}$ ($\text{RE} = \text{Er}, \text{Ho}, \text{Tm}$). *Vestnik SKFU*. 2017; (2): 21–26. (In Russ.)
- Mar'ina U. A., Vorob'ev V. A., Mar'in A. P. Vliyanie kontsentratsii primesi Yb i tipa plavnaya na lyuminescentnyye svoystva $\text{CaSnO}_3 : \text{Yb}$ [Influence of concentration of Yb impurity and type of mineralizer on luminescent properties $\text{CaSnO}_3 : \text{Yb}$]. Nauchnye issledovaniya i razrabotki molodykh uchenykh: materialy XIV mezhdunar. molodezhnoi nauchno-prakt. konf = *Research and development of young scientists: materials XIV of the international youth scientific and practical conference*. Novosibirsk: Publishing House TsRNS, 2016. (In Russ.)
- Tao Pang, Wenhui Lu, Wujian Shen. Chromaticity modulation of upconversion luminescence in $\text{CaSnO}_3 : \text{Yb}^{3+}, \text{Er}^{3+}, \text{Li}^+$ phosphors through Yb³⁺ concentration, pumping power and temperature. *Physica B: Condensed Matter*. 2016; 502: 11–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physb.2016.08.036>
- Castelli I. E., Olsen T., Datta S., Landis D. D., Dahl S., Thygesen K. S., Jacobsen K. W. Computational screening of perovskite metal oxides for optimal solar light capture. *Energy Environ. Sci.* 2012; 5(2): 5814–5819. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C1EE02717D>
- Henriques J. M., Caetano E. W. S., Freire V. N., da Costa J. A. P., Albuquerque E. L. Structural, electronic, and optical absorption properties of orthorhombic CaSnO_3 through *ab initio* calculations. *J. Physics: Condensed Matter*. 2007; 19(10): 106214 (1–9). <https://doi.org/10.1088/0953-8984/19/10/106214>
- Protasov N. M. *Strukturnoe modelirovanie slozhnykh oksidov so strukturoi perovskita v chastichno kovalentnom priblizhenii* [Structural modeling of complex oxides with structure of a perovskite in partially covalent approach]. Moscow: MGU im. M. V. Lomonosova, 2011, 51 p. (In Russ.)
- Savikin A. P., Grishin I. A. *Sintez keramicheskikh obraztsov ZBLAN : Ho³⁺ i ZBLAN : Ho³⁺-Yb³⁺ i issledovanie antistoksovoi lyuminesentsii* [Synthesis of ceramic samples of ZBLAN : Ho^{3+} both ZBLAN : $\text{Ho}^{3+}\text{-Yb}^{3+}$ and research of an anti-Stokes luminescence: educational and methodical grant]. Nizhny Novgorod: Nats. issled. NGU im. N. I. Lobachevskogo, 2016, 18 p. (In Russ.)
- Solid-state lasers with semiconductor pump of short- and average IR-ranges (2 micron, 3–8 micron) on the basis of crystals and ceramics, activated by ions Tm и Ho. Report on research work, head Ryabochkina P. A.; performers: Antipov O. L., Chuprunov E. V., Lomonova E. E. Saransk, 2012, 83 p. (In Russ.)
- Bailey D., Wright E. *Volokonnaya optika: teoriya i praktika* [Practical fiber optics]. Moscow: KUDITs-PRESS, 2008, p. 98. (In Russ.)
- Shakhno E. A. *Fizicheskie osnovy primeneniya lazerov v meditsine* [Physical bases of use of lasers in medicine]. St. Petersburg: NIU ITMO, 2012, 129 p. (In Russ.)